

Decoding the Molecular Basis of the Specificity of an anti-sTn Antibody

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sTn-antigen is a promising target for therapeutic and diagnostic applications, and for that purpose research efforts have been devoted to developing anti-sTn antibodies.^{1,2,3} However, the enhancement of the specificity of anti-sTn antibodies is of paramount importance for their use as tumour immunotherapeutic or/and diagnostic applications. In this context, for the elucidation of anti-sTn antibodies' specificity and for a rational improvement of their recognition towards cancer cells is essential to establish a robust structure-driven approach to decipher the molecular basis of anti-sTn antibodies' recognition. Through an integrative and multidisciplinary approach, the molecular determinants, behind the anti- α 2,6-sialic acid L2A5 antibody's specificity, were exhaustively scrutinized, and will be described in this presentation.

References

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